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Is there a gender gap in audit fees in Spain? Explaining the variables involved in audit fees

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Purpose: The main objective of this study is to analyse the impact of auditor gender on audit fees, with a view to establishing whether there are any differences in audit price depending on the gender of the auditor.

Motivation: The existence of a gender gap in audit fees is a problem. In order to try to reduce this gap, it is necessary to understand the determinants of audit fees according to gender.

Design/Methodology/Approach: The sample under analysis is made up of 3217 unlisted Spanish companies. In order to fulfil our aim, an audit fee model is put forward, applying a multiple linear regression analysis differentiated by auditor gender.

Main findings: The results point to an absence of any statistically significant association between audit fees and auditor gender. In contrast to other countries within the same context, Spanish female audit partners do not generate higher audit fees than their male counterparts; there is no female audit fee premium as there seems to be in other countries such as Belgium, France, Finland, China or the USA.

Practical implications: Differences were found among the factors which determine audit fees; there tend to be fewer factors considered in audits signed by female auditors, with indicators related to the economic and financial situation of the company under audit excluded from the fees model. These results could be justified by differences between male and female auditors with respect to audit planning and efficiency.

Novelty/Contribution: This paper is a contribution to the literature on gender in auditing, and offers up evidence on the impact of auditor gender on audit fees within a specific context that has not been studied in any depth, namely the Spanish auditing market for unlisted companies.

Keywords: audit fees; gender; women; audit partner

1. Introduction

Over the past two decades, there has been a growing interest among researchers to include the perspective of gender¹ in studies on accounting and auditing activities. Thus, the

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differences in knowledge, information processing, decision-making (Chung & Monroe, 2001; O'Donnell & Johnson, 2001), and in quality and audit fee levels between male and female auditors (Hardies et al., 2015, Itonen & Peni, 2012) have been explored. Other research has focused on analysing inequalities in terms of career progression or the glass ceiling in auditing (Cohen et al., 2020; Haynes, 2017).

The data related to auditing have pointed to increasing female representation, while simultaneously highlighting considerable differences in access to managerial positions (Adapa et al., 2016; Siboni et al., 2016). In spite of the existing gender gap in both the business world in general and the audit industry in particular (Almer et al., 2021; Cohen et al., 2020), the presence of women in the auditing field is constantly growing (AICPA, 2019; Jones et al., 2019). The percentage in absolute values (practising and non-practising) of female auditors in Spain is 25%, while it would seem that the number of audits signed by women tripled between 2012 and 2019 (DIBAF, 2020). The study carried out by Espinosa et al. (2021) indicates that the presence of women in large auditing firms is increasing annually, reaching 50% in some companies. However, the aforementioned researchers equally pointed out that this gender diversity was evidenced in lower positions in the audit companies, as opposed to leadership roles (partner and director), where men significantly outnumber women.

This inequality in the audit sector can be explained by the difficulties in changing stereotypes, maternity and work flexibility policies, among other causes (Haynes, 2017). It is worth pointing out that many of the work-life balance measures put in place by audit companies have had the opposite effect to what was expected (Dambrin & Lambert, 2012; Kornberger et al., 2010), such as continuing discriminatory practices (Hardies et al., 2021).

In this study we analyse the impact of the audit partner's gender on the determination of audit fees in an understudied context corresponding to the Spanish audit market of unlisted companies. The aim is to observe whether there are differences in the audit fee when the audit report is signed by a male or female partner.

We contribute to the gendered audit literature in several important ways. First, we add new evidence to the association between audit fees and audit partner gender. There are a very small number of published studies, and their results are limited as they refer to specific geographical areas (North-Central European countries, USA or China) and time periods of limited breadth (e.g. Burke et al. 2019; Hardies et al., 2015, 2021; Itonen & Peni, 2012; Lee et al., 2019; Liu, 2017). Secondly, we provide empirical evidence on the impact of auditor gender on audit fees in the specific context of the Spanish auditing market of unlisted companies (Aguilar et al., 2019). In this sense, it is worth pointing out that most of the research on audit fees is based on listed companies, and therefore the results may not be applicable to unlisted companies. Furthermore, the underlying reason for this focus on listed companies is that their data are easily accessed, and at no cost to the researchers. Consequently, the act of choosing unlisted companies for our study grants us access to information in a scarcely studied national context, as well as providing us with better representation and coverage. The recommendations in previous studies that the scope of research be broadened to include unlisted companies is thus justified (Krauß et al., 2015; Reheul et al., 2017). Thirdly, we contribute towards the evidence on both audited companies and auditing firms. Regarding audited companies, the scope of our research is broader than previous studies, given that a sample of unlisted companies is used; this includes a broad range of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs)², which make up the majority of the European and Spanish business market – in both cases accounting for 99.8% of companies (EC, 2023; DGYPYME, 2023) – and whose

particular characteristics could justify any potential differences in the results. As far as audit companies are concerned, our study has been extended to a more competitive auditing market; in contrast to audits of listed companies, which are grouped around the large multinationals, the classifications of individual auditors and audit companies of different sizes have been included. Together, they represent an important, although practically unexplored, part of this market (Burke et al., 2019).

The remainder of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 provides theoretical background and develops the hypotheses. Section 3 describes the research methodology. We report the results in Sections 4 and in Section 5 we include the discussion and conclusions of the paper. Finally, we identify the limitations of the research and suggest future lines of research.

2. Theoretical background and hypotheses

Regarding the association of audit fees and auditor gender, the scarcity of published studies should be noted, as well as the limited applicability of their findings, given that they deal with specific geographical areas and time periods that are usually limited in scope. Thus, most studies recognise the existence of a female audit fee premium linked to various factors, including the fact that female auditors exhibit better compliance with rules and regulations, have higher levels of moral reasoning, and are more ethical (Karjalainen et al., 2018), are also more effective in information processing (Chung & Monroe, 2001) and audit judgements (O'Donnell & Johnson, 2001), as well as the existence of a higher level of audit quality and higher levels of dedication or audit effort among female audit partners (Hardies et al., 2016; Ittonen et al., 2013). It is worth pointing out that this audit premium should be understood as income for the audit firm, as it does not always coincide with the auditor's earnings.

In the European context, one of the first benchmark studies in this area was that carried out by Ittonen and Peni (2012), who focused their investigation on listed companies (NASDAQ) in Finland, Denmark and Sweden. Their paper examines whether the gender of the audit engagement partner affects audit fees. Specifically, they examine the effect of auditor gender on audit fees in an environment where the responsible audit partners can be identified. The empirical results point to a statistically significant relation between audit fees and audit partner gender, suggesting that higher audit fees are associated with female audit partners. The findings are based on the fact that female auditors appear to invest more time in audit task planning and risk evaluation, which could lead to an increased audit effort and thereby higher audit fees. Furthermore, they point out that the higher quality offered by female audit partners could be perceived, valued and demanded by the clients themselves.

The existence of a female audit fee premium for Belgian firms was investigated by Hardies et al. (2015). They note that companies pay higher audit fees (approximately 7%) when the work is carried out by female audit partners. They point out that this audit premium could be due to gender differences regarding knowledge, skills, preferences and behaviour depending on the gender of the auditor, as well as factors related to the client, such as a demand for gender diversity, gender perceptions regarding audit quality or client satisfaction. This female audit fee premium in the Belgian market was later confirmed by Hardies et al. (2021). Also, the existence of a premium audit fee when the audit team includes a woman was investigated by Nekhili et al. (2018). They studied the impact of auditor gender on audit fees in France, where joint audits are compulsory by law. The study notes that when joint audits are carried out by partners of different genders, an audit

fee premium of 11% is applied, in contrast to exclusively male teams. The impact of audit team gender on audit fees will depend on the size of the firm and the audit team members. The existence of a female audit fee premium in Finland was also suggested by the study carried out by Kähäri (2020) in the Finnish auditing market.

There are few studies for the Spanish context, that by Aguilar et al. (2019) being worthy of mention. They investigated whether female audit partners in SME audit firms take into account a risk premium when fixing their fees. The study introduces an interesting factor regarding the measurement of audit effort (number of hours spent on the audit). The results suggest that the audited companies pay higher audit fees when the audit report is signed by a female audit partner. This premium is justified by female auditors' lower risk tolerance and increased audit effort. Nevertheless, the results obtained are difficult to generalise, given that the sample analysed is based on small and medium-sized auditing firms with limited representativeness in the sector, as well as the selection and size of the sample (data were requested from 21 auditing firms, with a response from only 11 of them).

In a non-European context, the research carried out by Li and Shi (2012) in China highlights the fact that the presence of female audit partners in audit reports signed by two auditors may increase earnings, while discretionary accruals may decrease and have a positive effect on audit fees. Continuing in the Chinese context, Liu (2017) carried out a study which pointed out that auditor gender shows a significant correlation with audit fees. The study findings indicate that audit clients are willing to pay higher audit fees for audits carried out by female auditors because they believe them to be more cautious and ethical workers. Huang et al. (2015) found that the audit fees in audits carried out by female auditors in Taiwan were significantly lower than those of their male counterparts. Nevertheless, they observed that the presence of female partners in an audit correlated positively with higher earnings, adding that the differences in audit fees could be explained by the existing discrimination towards women in Taiwan, in terms of work and salary. They suggest that stereotypes may vary among cultures, and that work discrimination against women is less severe in Northern European countries than in Taiwan, where Confucianism defends women staying at home and taking charge of domestic tasks while men lead the family as a social value (Yang et al., 2013). Hu et al. (2014) concluded that there was a significantly positive correlation between audit partner gender and audit fees. These findings are justified by the fact that more female auditors prefer to carry out auditing procedures and/or use more staff to reduce audit risk, which would increase the audit costs and thereby the audit fees. Also, Tamtomo and Fitriany (2019) indicate that Indonesian female audit partners generate higher audit fees than their male counterparts because they apply a greater audit effort, as well as having keener negotiating skills.

In spite of the profusion of literature on auditing in the United States, inclusion of the name of the audit partner in the audit report was not compulsory until 2017. Therefore, the publications that could point to a potential association between audit fees and auditor gender are limited in number and period range, as they only cover recent years. It is worth mentioning the study by Lee et al. (2019), which found an association between female audit partners and an audit fee premium, as well as with higher audit quality. In contrast, Burke et al. (2019) suggest that female audit partners charge higher audit fees in spite of there being no difference in audit quality between female and male audit partners. Liu and Xu (2021) qualify the results depending on type of auditing company, suggesting that the impact of audit partner gender on audit fees varies between BIG4 auditors and Non-BIG4 auditors; they found statistical significance for the former, and an absence of significance for the latter. Given the greater proportion of female-female auditor teams in the four large auditing multinationals, the difference could explain the "gender fee".

Taking the previously mentioned studies as a starting point, our aim is to examine the relationship between audit fees and audit partner gender in the Spanish context. We therefore put forward the following hypotheses:

Hypothesis 1 (H₁): There are significant differences in audit fees with respect to the gender of the audit partner.

Hypothesis 2 (H₂): There are significant differences in the variables that explain audit fees with respect to the gender of the audit partner.

Hypothesis 3 (H₃): The audit fees are explained by variables related to the auditor's personal attributes, by variables related to the type of auditor (corporate), by variables related to the audit exercise and by variables related to the audited company, while the weight of these variables differs according to gender.

3. Research methodology

3.1. Sample

The population under study here are unlisted Spanish companies audited between 2008 and 2015. In order to gather a representative sample of the population under study, we used the ARDÁN database.³ The sample choice was made via stratified sampling according to sectors, with replacement. An initial population of 131,195 firms was used as a starting point. Sample size was calculated by sector and year, with a margin of error of 5% and confidence level of 95%, with an acceptable level of heterogeneity at 50%. The final sample was made up of a total of 3217 observations, noting that 80% of the sample companies were SMEs.

3.2. Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were calculated. The next step was to carry out a means analysis using Student's t-test for dichotomous variables and the analysis of variance (ANOVA), followed by the Bonferroni post hoc test for polytomous variables. In order to establish the relation between the scale variables, Pearson's correlation was also calculated. Lastly, a regression model analysis was carried out in order to test the previously stated hypothesis. All the analyses were carried out with a confidence level of 95%.

3.3. Model for audit fees

In order to be able to contrast the hypothesis posed, an audit report lag model was put forward, with the following functional form:

$$\begin{aligned} LN_AFEE = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 GENDER + \beta_2 AGE + \beta_3 EXP + \beta_4 BIG4 + \beta_5 AUDITOR + \beta_6 NAS \\ & + \beta_7 SR_ARL + \beta_8 OPINION + \beta_9 LN_TA + \beta_{10} LOSS + \beta_{11} FINL + \beta_{12} LIQ \\ & + \beta_{13} ROA + \beta_{14} PROB_ZFC + \beta_{15} SR_SUBS - FO + \beta_{16} SR_SUBS - SP \\ & + \beta_{17} SR_EAT + \beta_{18} SECTOR + \varepsilon \end{aligned}$$

The dependent variable (LN_AFEE) represents the audit fees charged by the audit firms for the audit carried out. Our variable of interest is audit partner gender (GENDER), while we included a series of factors for the control variables; these factors have been previously documented in the literature related to personal audit partner attributes, type of auditor

Table 1. Description of the model variables and expected sign.

Variables	Definition and Codification	Expected sign
<i>Dependent variable</i>		
LN_AFEE	Natural logarithm of Audit fees.	
<i>Independent variables related to the personal attributes of the audit partner</i>		
GENDER	1 woman, 0 man	¿?
AGE	Age of the audit partner in reference to the date of the audit report.	+
EXP	Number of years from the date of registration of the auditor in the Official Registry of Auditors of Accounts (ROAC) until the closing date of the financial statements.	+
<i>Independent variables related to type of auditor (corporate)</i>		
BIG4	1 BIG4, 0 Otherwise	+
AUDITOR	3 Individual auditor, 2 Society, 1 Multinational, 0 BIG4	+
<i>Independent variables related to audit exercise</i>		
NAS	1 Provision of additional to audit services, 0 Otherwise.	+
SR_ARL	Square root of number of days between the end of accounting period and the signing of audit report.	-
OPINION	1 Qualified, 0 Unqualified	+
<i>Independent variables related to the audited company</i>		
LN_TA	Natural logarithm of total assets.	+
LOSS	1 if the company had losses in the year, 0 Otherwise	+
FINL	Total debt divided by total assets.	+
LIQ	Current assets divided current liabilities.	-
ROA	Return on assets. Calculated as operating income divided by total assets.	-
PROB_ZFC	1 indicates probability of bankruptcy, 0 Otherwise. This probability is calculated using the probability of bankruptcy of the Zmijewski model (1984).	+
SR_SUBS-FO	Square root of the number of foreign subsidiaries.	+
SR_SUBS-SP	Square root of the number of Spanish subsidiaries.	+
SR_EAT	Square root of the number of Economic Activities Tax (EAT).	+
SECTOR	Sector to which the company belongs. It was coded into five categories: 4 Services, 3 Retail, 2 Construction, 1 Industry, 0 Agriculture.	¿?

(corporate), audit exercise and the audited company (Hay, 2013). Table 1 presents the variables used in the model and the expected sign for each one in relation to the response variable. The expected sign for each variable was determined based on the previous literature. The dependent variable and some of the independent variables have been transformed via the natural logarithm or the square root, in order to limit variability and obtain more robust results (Carson & Fargher, 2007).

Variables related to the personal attributes of the audit partner

Among the individual audit partner characteristics, we find gender of the person in charge of the audit (GENDER) and their experience, for which the most frequently used indicators were auditor age (AGE) (Chi et al., 2017) and years of experience as an auditor (EXP), specifically the number of years from the date of registration of the auditor in the Official Registry of Auditors of Accounts until the closing date of the financial statements (Kähäri, 2020).

Variables related to type of auditor (corporate)

The question of whether BIGN auditing companies charge higher audit fees than other audit firms has been broadly researched in the previous literature (Cunha-Silva et al., 2020; Fuentes & Sierra-Grau, 2015; Hay & Knechel, 2017). In general terms, larger audit firms have been observed in studies of unlisted companies (Peel & Roberts, 2003) to charge an audit fee premium. We have included two variables related to auditor type, BIG4 and AUDITOR. This last variable is coded in four categories: individual auditor, companies, multinationals and BIG4. This is in line with the more diverse structure of the Spanish auditing market for unlisted companies (Escaloni & Mareque, 2021).

Variables related to audit exercise

Another of the variables studied in fees models are non-audit fees, that is, those fees charged by auditing companies for services rendered other than auditing services (NAS). A considerable number of the studies point to the existence of a positive association between the two types of fees (Bhattacharya & Banerjee, 2020).

As a measure of audit efficiency, we included the variable audit report lag (ARL). Greater speed in issuing a report demands more auditing resources and time dedication. Audited companies may be willing to pay higher audit fees in order to speed up the auditing process and issuance of the audit report. Lee et al. (2009) and Khoufi and Khoufi (2018) suggest that “fast” audit reports are linked to audit fees premium. We also included the variable OPINION in our audit fee model, with the expectation of an association between a qualified opinion and greater audit effort, as in previous studies (Guzmán-Raja et al., 2021; Hay, 2013).

Variables related to the audited company

Audit fee models include variables related to the size of the client company, indicating the existence of a positive determining relationship between audit fees total and client company size (Guzmán-Raja et al., 2021). The most commonly used measure is total assets (TA) (Hay, 2013).

Regarding the economic-financial risk indicators of the audited company, and in line with recent studies, the variable losses (LOSS) is incorporated as a measure of client risk (Kähäri, 2020; Liu & Xu, 2021). Furthermore, we consider another series of variables included in previous studies, such as: i) ROA: return on assets (Abbasi et al., 2020; Ittonen & Peni, 2012; Fuentes & Sierra-Grau, 2015), ii) FINL: debt (Basioudis & Francis, 2007; Venkataraman et al., 2008), iii) LIQ: liquidity (De Lima Castro et al., 2015; Serrano-Madrid et al., 2013) and iv) PROB_ZFC: probability of bankruptcy of the Zmijewski model (1984) (Cenciarelli et al., 2018; Matozza et al. 2020).

Regarding complexity measures, the number of subsidiaries, both national and foreign (SUBS-FO and SUBS-SP) (Hay, 2013), are considered on the one hand, while other additional indicators such as the number of Economic Activities Tax (EAT) are taken into account on the other hand. EAT captures the total number of business segments that the audited company has (Widmann et al., 2021).

Last of all, we included the variable SECTOR, since some sectors are more difficult to audit due to factors such as having a larger volume of inventories and/or accounts payable, which in turn could lead to increased audit fees. Based on previous research in the Spanish context (Escaloni & Mareque, 2021; López-Corrales & Pedrosa, 2020), the variable

SECTOR was coded into five categories: agriculture, industry, construction, retail and services.

4. Results

4.1. Descriptive statistics and univariate analysis

As shown in Table 2, 14% of the reports in the sample were signed by women. The Student's T-test reveals there are no significant differences for LN_AFEE between the male and female audit partners ($p=0.478$), hence hypothesis 1 is rejected. Therefore, the next step was to check which variables impact audit fees for male and female audit partners separately, in order to establish whether or not they are the same.

Moreover, we attempted to determine the existence of significant differences for the dependent variable LN_AFEE, depending on whether the audit report is signed by a male audit partner or a female one. Tables 3 and 4 present these results.

Regarding male audit partners, Table 3 shows the existence of significant differences in five of the six independent variables analysed. NAS, OPINION, BIG4, LOSS and PROB_ZFC were seen to be significant at 1%. For female audit partners, there were only significant differences at 1% for the variables NAS and BIG4.

As Table 4 shows, there are significant differences in the polytomous variables SECTOR and AUDITOR for both male and female audit partners, significant at 1%. The Bonferroni test revealed the groups in which there are significant differences for both male and female audit partners. It is worth noting that there are significant differences for both male and female audit partners in the variable SECTOR. The agriculture sector presents the lowest average value of LN_AFEE for both male and female audit partners (men: 9.17; women: 9.06). In addition, for the variable AUDITOR, it is the BIG4 which have the highest average values of LN_AFEE for both male and female audit partners (men: 10.05; women: 10.11).

4.2. Multivariate analysis

Table 5 presents the correlation between the quantitative variables studied here. In general, it can be observed that the correlation levels are low, with the exception of the variable LN_TA for both male and female auditors (0.693 and 0.673, respectively).

In order to test hypothesis 3, we carried out a multiple linear regression analysis. The Student t-test for LN_AFEE rules out the existence of significant differences based on auditor gender. Nevertheless, the tests carried out suggest the existence of statistically significant differences with respect to the variables which impact determination of audit fees based on the auditor's gender. This justifies using differentiated regression models for male and female audit partners, the results of which are presented in Table 6.

With the aim of obtaining a better fit in the models, only those variables which – according to the previous analyses – proved to have a statistically significant relation/

Table 2. Descriptive statistics for variable LN_AFEE based on GENDER of the audit partners.

	N	Min	Max	Mean	S.D.	t	Sig.
Woman	450	7.97	12.77	9.44	0.8144	-0.710	0.478
Man	2767	7.82	14.16	9.41	0.8083		

Table 3. Test t-Student for LN_AFEE based on independent variables for male and female audit partners.

Variable	Codification	Woman					Man				
		N	Mean	S.D.	t	Sig.	N	Mean	S.D.	t	Sig.
NAS	Yes	77	10.07	0.9983	63.496	0.000**	544	9.99	0.9651	395.963	0.000**
	No	373	9.31	0.7050			2223	9.27	0.6956		
OPINION	Qualified	106	9.54	0.8706	-1.485	0.138	673	9.49	0.7865	-3.043	0.002**
	Unqualified	344	9.41	0.7949			2094	9.38	0.8136		
BIG4	Yes	142	10.11	0.8934	-12.037	0.000**	915	10.05	0.9022	-29.839	0.000**
	No	308	9.13	0.5484			1852	9.09	0.5192		
LOSS	Yes	109	9.39	0.7523	0.779	0.436	661	9.53	0.8760	-4.261	0.000**
	No	341	9.46	0.8336			2106	9.37	0.7821		
PROB-ZFC	Yes	112	9.50	0.8674	-0.814	0.417	616	9.51	0.8618	-3.234	0.001**
	No	338	9.42	0.7964			2151	9.38	0.7904		

Note: ** p < 0.01 indicate significance; Woman: N = 450; Man: N = 2767. The definition and measurement of the variables are described in Table 1.

Table 5. Correlations matrix for male and female audit partners.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
LN_AFEE (1)	1									
LN_TA (2)	Man 0.693**	1								
EXP (3)	Man -0.037	Woman -0.070**	1							
AGE (4)	Man -0.069	Woman -0.036	Man 0.808**	1						
ROA (5)	Man -0.147**	Woman -0.099**	Man 0.743**	Woman 0.063	1					
FINL (6)	Man -0.015	Woman -0.008	Man -0.001	Woman 0.022	Man -0.381**	1				
LIQ (7)	Man 0.117**	Woman 0.056**	Man -0.072**	Woman -0.095**	Man -0.337**	Woman 0.149**	1			
SR_SUBS-FO (8)	Man -0.140**	Woman -0.094*	Man 0.008	Woman -0.005	Man 0.085**	Woman -0.370**	Man -0.389**	1		
SR_SUBS-SP (9)	Man -0.103**	Woman -0.015	Man 0.007	Woman 0.037	Man 0.094*	Woman 0.103*	Man -0.105*	Woman 0.103*	1	
SR_EAT (10)	Man 0.377**	Woman 0.416**	Man -0.045*	Woman -0.070**	Man 0.037	Woman -0.002	Man -0.048*	Woman -0.048*	Man 0.340**	1
SR_ARL (11)	Man 0.237**	Woman 0.473**	Man 0.097*	Woman 0.076	Man 0.049	Woman -0.071	Man -0.056	Woman -0.047*	Man 0.497**	Woman 0.336**
	Man 0.278**	Woman 0.424**	Man -0.017	Woman -0.019	Man 0.045*	Woman 0.009	Man -0.047*	Woman 0.047**	Man 0.257**	Woman 0.295**
	Man 0.312**	Woman 0.351**	Man 0.028	Woman 0.036	Man 0.017	Woman 0.041	Man -0.123**	Woman -0.067**	Man 0.209**	Woman 0.209**
	Man 0.264**	Woman 0.301**	Man -0.029	Woman -0.024	Man -0.001	Woman 0.015	Man -0.022	Woman -0.089	Man -0.019	Woman 0.004
	Man -0.170**	Woman -0.151	Man -0.055	Woman -0.013	Man -0.044	Woman 0.049	Man -0.022	Woman -0.071**	Man -0.045*	Woman -0.007
	Man -0.134**	Woman -0.144**	Man 0.011	Woman 0.022	Man -0.057**	Woman 0.066**	Man -0.007	Woman -0.071**	Man -0.045*	Woman -0.007

Note: *, ** p < 0.05, 0.01 indicate significance. The definition and measurement of the variables are described in Table 1.

Table 6. Results of linear regression for male and female audit partners.

	Model for Woman					Model for Man					
	Expected Sign	Model Coefficient	β	t	Sig.	VIF	Model Coefficient	β	t	Sig.	VIF
(Constant)		9.261		51.613	0.000**		9.057		119.255	0.000**	
EXP	+						-0.001	-0.011	-0.910	0.363	1.055
BIG4	+	0.615	0.351	11.010	0.000**	1.244	0.519	0.302	21.206	0.000**	1.370
NAS	+	0.234	0.108	3.475	0.001**	1.190	0.215	0.106	8.110	0.000**	1.145
SR_ARL	-	-0.028	-0.062	-2.021	0.044*	1.137	-0.014	-0.036	-2.877	0.004**	1.067
OPINION	+						0.040	0.021	1.706	0.088	1.044
LN_TA	+	0.278	0.482	13.365	0.000**	1.590	0.281	0.468	30.451	0.000**	1.594
LOSS	+						0.093	0.049	3.842	0.000**	1.111
FINL	+	0.062	0.033	1.030	0.303	1.248	0.151	0.057	3.289	0.001**	2.003
LIQ	-	-0.006	-0.019	-0.617	0.538	1.214	-0.008	-0.028	-2.060	0.039*	1.223
PROB_ZFC	+						-0.072	-0.037	-2.246	0.025*	1.851
SR_SUBS-FO	+	0.075	0.074	2.281	0.023*	1.302	0.081	0.098	7.226	0.000**	1.240
SR_EAT	+	0.063	0.047	1.487	0.138	1.237	0.080	0.062	4.732	0.000**	1.155
Agriculture	?	-0.183	-0.043	-1.428	0.154	1.101	-0.031	-0.009	-0.655	0.513	1.160
Industry	?	0.194	0.104	3.067	0.002**	1.412	0.144	0.083	5.418	0.000**	1.587
Retail	?	0.200	0.113	3.290	0.001**	1.437	0.133	0.074	4.846	0.000**	1.554
Construction	?	-0.062	-0.022	-0.670	0.503	1.267	-0.160	-0.055	-4.013	0.000**	1.273
R ²		0.643					0.593				
R ² Adjusted		0.633					0.59				
Durbin-Watson		1.915					1.888				
N		450					2767				

Note: *, ** p < 0.05, 0.01 indicate significance. Dependent variable: LN_AFEF. The definition and measurement of the variables are described in Table 1.

association with the dependent variable LN_AFEE were included in each of them. The variables with risk of collinearity and a high correlation were ruled out.

Table 6 presents both the estimated coefficients (non-standardised) of the models, and the typified coefficients (standardised) named β , which reflect the specific weight of each variable in the model, indicating which of the group of independent variables has a greater impact. The last two columns present the value of the statistic and its significance. The statistic presents values with a degree of significance below 5%. The last column shows the values corresponding to the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), all of them below 10, which suggests that there is no multicollinearity or internal correlations between the independent variables. The value of adjusted coefficient of determination R^2 indicates that the model is capable of explaining approximately 59% and 63.3% of the variations of dependent variable (LN_AFEE) for male and female audit partners, respectively, considering a confidence level of 95%.

For the model of male audit partners, the variables were significant and the expected sign was verified, with the exception of the variables EXP, OPINION and the agriculture sector. BIG4, NAS, SR_ARL, LN_TA, LOSS, FINL, SR_SUBS-FO, SR_EAT and the industry, retail and construction sectors were significant at 1%, while the variables LIQ and PROB_ZFC were significant at 5%. The variables LN_TA and BIG4 are the factors which present higher standardised beta coefficients ($\beta=0.468$ and $\beta=0.302$).

For the female audit partner model, only the variables BIG4, NAS, LN_TA, and the industry and retail sectors were significant at 1%, while SR_ARL and SR_SUBS-FO were significant at 5%. In line with the model for men, the variables LN_TA and BIG4 are the factors that present the highest standardised beta coefficients ($\beta=0.482$ and $\beta=0.351$).

5. Discussion and conclusions

This study fits within the area of audit research from a gender perspective, with the main objective of analysing the impact of auditor gender on audit fees. Our work can contribute several aspects that are either new or of interest. This research incorporates variables into the audit fees model that have scarcely been dealt with the previous literature, namely individual attributes of the audit partner (gender and experience). Furthermore, the context of our study – unlisted Spanish companies – is an audit market that has been the object of very little research.

The empirical results of this study on the impact of audit partner gender on audit fees determination suggest that there is little association between the two variables, which leads us to reject the first hypothesis. In fact, our results contrast with previous studies which pointed to a female audit premium, studies including those carried out by Hardies et al. (2015, 2021) in Belgium, Nekhili et al. (2018) in France, Kähäri (2020) in Finland, Lee et al. (2019) in the USA or Liu (2017) in China. The differences in the results could be explained by the differences in context and particularities of the different audit markets. On the one hand, the high concentration of the Spanish audit market, the second highest in the European Union (CNMC, 2019), and the better reputation of the audit multinationals in Spain – with a better brand image – could preclude the consideration of individual audit partner attributes (among these, audit partner gender and the possible quality premium associated to female audit partners) in the client's perception of quality, and therefore in audit fee negotiation factors (Lee et al., 2019). Clients generally believe that large auditing firms can offer higher quality audits (Gray & Ratzinger, 2010), so brand effect has a significant impact on companies' market power; it is a determining factor in audit price determination that has greater weight than valuation of the audit partner's personal

attributes (Lee et al., 2019; Ruiz-Barbadillo et al., 2021). The size of the Spanish auditing market, with its considerable number of auditing companies, could also have an impact on the weak assessment of the audit partner's individual gender attributes, in contrast with the status quo in smaller markets where it is easier to establish individual reputation (Kähäri, 2020).

In terms of the client's side, the way audit work is organised – carried out by work teams mainly based in large multinationals and audit companies of a certain size – could go some way to explaining the absence of gender-based differences in the Spanish context. The greater weight of the audit team members could explain why individual audit partner attributes have less influence in determining audit fees (Annelin, 2019; Deloitte, 2021).

In the same line, the barriers hindering career development and discriminatory practices towards female auditors, where applicable (Hardies et al., 2021), could mean that the quality premium referred to in the previous literature which seems to be associated with female auditors, may not actually figure in the income they receive, and therefore are not shown in the audit fees.

In addition, this study has analysed what the determinants of audit fees are. As in previous research in Spain such as Cunha-Silva et al. (2020) or López-Corrales and Pedrosa (2020), audit fees are mainly determined by the type of auditor (BIG4), by variables related to audit exercise (audit report lag and provision of additional audit services) and, by the size, complexity and risk indicators of the audited company. Specifically, as revealed by the results of this study, our research has shown which factors impact audit fees of male and female audit partners and point to there being some differences between the two genders. The differential analyses based on audit partner gender point to differences in the perception and assessment of audit effort, and therefore in determining factors of audit fees.

Focusing mainly on the differences found between the two estimated models (woman/man), there is a decrease in the factors under consideration when the audit is carried out by female auditors, and specifically in the variables related to the economic-financial situation and the complexity of the audited company. Indicators relating to the economic and financial situation of the audited company are excluded from the women's model (LOSS, FINL, LIQ, PROB_ZFC). These findings could be backed up by research such as that carried out by Bustos-Contell et al. (2022), which identified differences when audit teams are led by women. These researchers hold that women are more efficient at processing information during the planning and audit stage. The results of their study suggest that female-led audit teams are more efficient than those led by men, requiring less audit hours for each audit engagement, and therefore “audit effort is more efficient”.

Regarding complexity factors, the number of Economic Activities Tax (EAT) and the agriculture and construction sectors are excluded in our women's model. The agriculture sector is equally excluded in the men's model, while the other two factors are statistically significant. The relation between the construction sector and audit fees has been observed in previous studies in the Spanish context (Guzmán-Raja et al., 2021; López-Corrales & Pedrosa, 2020). López-Corrales and Pedrosa (2020) identified a significant relation with a negative sign between audit fees and the company belonging to the construction sector for a sample of SMEs during the pre-crisis financial period (2006–2007) and the financial crisis (2008–2010). They justified this result through the excessive protagonism in the Spanish economy of the construction sector, which is precisely the most badly hit in financial crises. There would therefore be more pressure from the audited companies for costs to be reduced, including audit fees. Based on a sample mostly made up of unlisted Spanish companies (98.7% of the sample) between 2013 and 2018, Guzmán-Raja et al. (2021) also found a statistically

significant relation between audit fees and the construction sector, but in this case with a positive sign. Regarding the variable number of EAT which captures the total number of business segments owned by the company, while this is a measure specific to the Spanish context, other international studies also use similar measures, obtaining a significant relation with audit fees (Goodwin & Wu 2014, Carcello et al., 2002).

We have also observed that the audit fees of both genders are higher in BIG4 audit firms in the following cases: when the audited company contracts non-audit services (NAS), when the audit report lag is low (SR_ARL), the larger the audited company is (LN_TA), the more foreign subsidiaries owned by the audited company (SR_SUBS-FO) and whether its productive sector is industry or retail. While it is true that the evidence on the relation between audit fees and the gender-based variables described above is scarce, we can cite some approximations such as those observed in the studies by Hardies et al. (2015, 2021) and Nekhili (2018).

The contributions derived from this article allow us to ascertain whether there is a gender-based difference in audit fees in Spain, with a view to promoting transparency, equality, competition and regulation fulfilment in the audit market, which in turn would benefit audited companies, the auditors themselves and the general public.

6. Limitations and future lines of research

This study has certain limitations. In the first place, there are other individual audit partner attributes which could be considered, such as specialisation. Secondly, this study has been carried out in the Spanish market of unlisted companies, so its results cannot be directly extrapolated to other contexts of a different size and/or level of concentration. Lastly, there is a limitation related to the period of time chosen for this statistical analysis (2008–2015). Nevertheless, we consider that the inclusion of the years directly after this period would not imply any substantial change to our results, apart from 2020 and the following years, given the singularity of the COVID-19 crisis. The specific characteristics of this pandemic and its obvious and particular effects on digitalisation and re-organisation of work in terms of place and time are an opportunity to consider the impact of the pandemic on changes in female auditors' professional career and audit fee models in future research.

In considering future research from a gender perspective, we first propose examining the association between the incomes of male and female audit partners and audit fees, alert to the potential existence of work and/or salary discrimination. Secondly, it would be worth extending the study to take into account the other members of audit teams in the audit fee model, specifically to evaluate the members of the audit teams and incorporate individual attributes of the other team members, mainly the audit engagement manager.

Declaration of interest

The authors declare that they have no competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Authorship contributions

Conceptualisation: M.M. and S.E.; formal analysis: M.M. and S.E.; investigation: M.M. and S.E.; methodology: M.M.; software: M.M.; supervision: M.M. and S.E.; validation: M.M. and S.E.; writing – original draft: M.M. and S.E.; writing – review and editing: M.M. Both authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Notes

1. Gender is proxied by biological sex, which was determined by the full name of the partner.
2. The parameters to the definition of SME as stipulated in Commission Delegated Directive (EU) 2023/2775 of 17 October 2023 (EU, 2023).
3. ARDÁN database, a business support service that is part of the Consortium of the Duty-Free Zone of Vigo.

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